

Impact of drug–drug interactions in hospitalised COVID-19 patients: association with polytherapy, comorbidities, and disease severity

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Abstract

Introduction: Drug–drug interactions (DDIs) influence treatment outcomes, particularly in complex diseases such as coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). This study aimed to evaluate the impact of DDIs in COVID-19 patients.

Materials and methods: A study was conducted on 200 patients with mild, moderate, or severe COVID-19 infections. Next, DDIs were classified into five risk categories (A–X).

Results: Altogether, 1689 DDIs were identified (maximum of 64 per patient). Most interactions were category C (65.3%). Clinically significant DDIs (C–X) accounted for 73.6% of interactions. Positive correlations were found between the total number of DDIs and both the total number of drugs (very strong) and comorbidities/diagnoses (strong). Patients with severe COVID-19 infections had significantly more DDIs and drugs used. Polypharmacy was highly frequent (97.5%, average of 9.9 drugs per patient).

Conclusion: Overall, COVID-19 patients often have clinically significant DDIs resulting from polypharmacy and comorbidities, especially in severe cases. Systematic DDI assessment is essential.

Keywords

comorbidity, COVID-19, drug–drug interaction, polypharmacy

Introduction

Drug–drug interactions (DDIs) represent one of the main factors that can affect the success of treatment, especially in cases of complex therapeutic protocols that include the use of multiple drugs from different therapeutic groups (McQuade and Campbell 2021). Due to the complex nature of the disease and impaired function of numerous organs, polypharmacy in coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19)

patients can hardly be avoided, which is why there is a realistically high risk of DDIs among patients (Khiali and Entezari-Maleki 2020). Proinflammatory cytokines can interact with cell membrane receptors and transporters on the vascular endothelium and parenchymal cells of various organs. Inflammation and immune reactions represent significant factors that can affect the function of specific transport proteins on cell membranes, which mediate the translocation of drugs into and out of cells, as well as the activity

of enzymes involved in drug metabolism. Many transcription factors are activated during inflammation and play a key role in the regulation of transporters and enzymes (Sun et al. 2023). The inflammatory component in COVID-19 patients is also responsible for modifying the concentration of blood proteins, which can significantly impair drug distribution. The alteration of transport proteins and enzymes can result in modified drug pharmacokinetics and an unexpected therapeutic response (Kumar and Trivedi 2021).

This study aimed to examine how polypharmacy, comorbidities, and disease severity are associated with the frequency of DDIs in hospitalised COVID-19 patients.

Materials and methods

The study was designed as a single-centre, retrospective-prospective study. The analysed data were obtained from medical records, discharge letters, and other medical documentation of patients hospitalised in General Hospital Tešanj from July 2020 to November 2021. It included 200 COVID-19 patients who were older than 18; of both sexes; had a diagnosis of COVID-19 infection; were hospitalised for at least two weeks; and had a mild ($n = 76$), moderate ($n = 70$), or severe ($n = 54$) clinical picture. Minors, pregnant and nursing women, as well as asymptomatic patients and patients in critical condition, were excluded.

The classification of COVID-19 patients according to the severity of the clinical picture at admission (the degree of seriousness of the symptoms and clinical manifestations of a disease, reflecting the potential impact on the patients' health and the need for medical intervention) was performed based on the references by Baj et al. (2020) and Nishiura et al. (2020).

The evaluation of the frequency of occurrence and the classification of DDIs according to the risk assessment were performed using the software program UpToDate® Lexidrug™ (UpToDate Inc., Wolters Kluwer Health, the United States of America). Interactions were classified according to the risk assessment into five categories: A, B, C, D, and X:

- A, neither pharmacodynamic nor pharmacokinetic DDI;
- B, drugs may interact with each other, but there is little or no evidence of clinical concern arising from their concomitant use;
- C, therapeutic monitoring is recommended, even though the benefits of concomitant use usually outweigh the risks;
- D, therapy modification is recommended; a patient-specific assessment must be performed to determine whether the benefits of concomitant use outweigh the risks;
- X, risks usually outweigh the benefits, so these combinations are generally considered contraindicated and should be avoided.

Thus, DDIs of categories A and B were clinically insignificant and did not require any measures or interventions, while those of C, D, and X were considered clinically significant.

Statistical data processing was performed using Microsoft Excel 2021 (Microsoft Corporation, the United States of America) and IBM® SPSS Statistics 26 (IBM®, the United States of America). The significance level was $\alpha = 0.05$. The normality of data distribution was tested by the Kolmogorov–Smirnov and the Shapiro–Wilk tests. The results of the correlation analyses were expressed by the Spearman correlation coefficient (ρ):

- $\rho < 0.19$, very weak correlation;
- $0.20 < \rho < 0.39$, weak correlation;
- $0.40 < \rho < 0.59$, moderate correlation;
- $0.60 < \rho < 0.79$, strong correlation;
- $0.80 < \rho < 1.00$, very strong correlation.

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of General Hospital Tešanj (reference number: 01-4-18/21) and the Ethics Committee of the University of Sarajevo – Faculty of Pharmacy (reference number: 0101-3220/22). The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki for research involving human subjects. Participants in the study provided written informed consent for voluntary participation.

Results and discussion

The total number of DDIs in all patients was 1689. The highest number of DDIs in one patient was 64. In addition to COVID-19 infection (severe clinical picture), that patient also had 11 comorbidities. The largest number of DDIs was from risk category C (therapeutic monitoring is recommended; $n = 1103$), then risk category B (no activity required; $n = 445$), then risk category X (avoid therapy; $n = 80$) and D (therapy modification is recommended; $n = 61$), while there were no interactions from risk category A (no known interaction). The most common interaction from risk category B was dexamethasone–beclomethasone/formoterol, from risk category C methylprednisolone–furosemide, from risk category D rivaroxaban–diclofenac, and from risk category X azithromycin–bilastine. The 10 most common DDIs from risk categories B, C, D, and X are shown in Table 1.

The results of our study showed an extremely high frequency of both polypharmacy and DDIs. Defining polypharmacy as the simultaneous use of five or more drugs, it was noted that 195 (97.5%) patients were on polypharmacy [106 (53%) on moderate polypharmacy (number of drugs: 5–9); 89 (44.5%) on extensive polypharmacy (number of drugs: 10 or more)]. Patients received an average of 9.9 drugs, and the highest number of drugs used in one patient was 24. Other studies also showed a high frequency of polypharmacy: 63.9% (Cantudo-Cuenca et al. 2021) and 82% (Spanakis et al. 2022). The average number of drugs per patient during hospitalisation was 9.55 ± 2.71 (Rahmadani et al. 2023), similar to our results. Severe cases of COVID-19 infection were also more common in polypharmacy patients. A study by McQueenie et al. (2020) revealed a

Table 1. The 10 most common drug–drug interactions (DDIs) from each risk category.

Risk category	Interaction	<i>n</i>
B	beclomethasone and formoterol – dexamethasone	65
	rivaroxaban – azithromycin	64
	rivaroxaban – dexamethasone	40
	beclomethasone and formoterol – methylprednisolone	25
	azithromycin – loperamide	19
	budesonide and formoterol - dexamethasone	15
	budesonide and formoterol - methylprednisolone	14
	metformin - pantoprazole	13
	aminophylline - furosemide	12
	theophylline - furosemide	10
C	methylprednisolone - furosemide	32
	cefazolin - furosemide	28
	metformin - dexamethasone	25
	furosemide - dexamethasone	24
	metformin - methylprednisolone	21
	glimepiride - dexamethasone	19
	neutral protamine Hagedorn (NPH) insulin - dexamethasone	19
	neutral protamine Hagedorn (NPH) insulin - methylprednisolone	18
	fraxiparine - acetylsalicylic acid	16
	glimepiride - metformin	16
D	rivaroxaban - diclofenac	4
	rivaroxaban - acetylsalicylic acid	3
	rivaroxaban - ibuprofen	3
	acetylsalicylic acid - ibuprofen	2
	azithromycin - amiodarone	2
	dexamethasone - sodium bicarbonate	2
	furosemide - ibuprofen	2
	glimepiride - vildagliptin	2
	heparin - diclofenac	2
	heparin - ibuprofen	2
X	bilastine - azithromycin	15
	diazepam - metronidazole	13
	carbocisteine - metronidazole	12
	furosemide - promazine	11
	promazine - lisinopril and hydrochlorothiazide	11
	fluticasone and salmeterol - carvedilol	3
	salbutamol - carvedilol	3
	beclomethasone and formoterol - budesonide and formoterol	2
	budesonide and formoterol - fluticasone and salmeterol	2
	diclofenac - acemetacin	2

clear dose–response relationship between polypharmacy and increased risk of COVID-19 infection.

In general, drugs with anticholinergic, sedative, and respiratory depressant effects, as well as some drugs affecting the gastrointestinal system, were more likely to increase the risk of adverse outcomes in COVID-19 patients (Iloanus et al. 2021). In our study, apart from drugs prescribed for the control of COVID-19 infection, including corticosteroids and anticoagulants, the most prescribed were systemic anti-infectives, as well as drugs for the treatment of cardiovascular and gastrointestinal diseases.

The total number of interactions in the sample of all patients ($n = 200$) was 1689, with 527 DDI combinations. Clinically significant DDIs (risk category C–X)

accounted for 73.65% of all DDIs, which is slightly higher than in a study by Kilit et al. (2022), in which the share of clinically significant DDIs in the total number of recorded interactions was 65.5%.

In addition, DDIs were not recorded in 29 (14.5%) patients who were on polypharmacy, while in 26 (13%) patients only DDIs assessed as not requiring any intervention (risk category B) were recorded. The frequency of clinically significant DDIs was very high (72.5%). These results are consistent with the results of Cantudo-Cuenca et al. (2021), where DDIs were detected in 152 (87.4%) out of 174 hospitalised COVID-19 patients, with clinically significant DDIs identified in 81.1% and contraindications in 14.6% of them.

Interactions from risk category B were observed in 146 (73%) patients. The number of these DDIs ranged from one to 15 per patient. The share of DDIs from risk category B in the total number of interactions (26.35%) was slightly lower than in a study by Kilit et al. (2022), in which, among 605 DDIs in hospitalised COVID-19 patients, 186 (30.7%) DDIs from risk category B were detected. Analysing DDIs from risk category B, 85 DDI combinations that fall into this category were found. The most common DDI was dexamethasone–beclomethasone/formoterol. Both drugs belong to the same therapeutic group (corticosteroids), and their simultaneous use can increase the risk of hypokalaemia. Nevertheless, DDIs from this risk category carry a small clinical risk for the patient and do not require corrective measures.

Interactions from risk category C were observed in 119 (59.5%) patients and accounted for the largest part of all detected interactions. The share of DDIs from risk category C in the total number of interactions (65.3%) was slightly higher than in a study by Kilit et al. (2022), in which, among 605 DDIs in hospitalised COVID-19 patients, 339 (56%) DDIs from risk category C were detected. Analysing DDIs from risk category C, 386 DDI combinations that fall into this category were found. Combinations of corticosteroids (dexamethasone and methylprednisolone) with antihyperglycaemics (metformin, glimepiride, and neutral protamine Hagedorn (NPH) insulin), as well as corticosteroids with drugs for the treatment of cardiovascular diseases (furosemide, lisinopril, and hydrochlorothiazide), had the highest frequency. Interactions of corticosteroids with acetylsalicylic acid were also common.

Interactions from risk category D were observed in 29 (14.5%) patients. The number of these DDIs ranged from two to six per patient. The share of DDIs from risk category D in the total number of interactions (3.61%) was significantly lower than in a study by Kilit et al. (2022), in which, among 605 DDIs in hospitalised COVID-19 patients, 54 (8.9%) DDIs from risk category D were detected. Analysing DDIs from risk category D, 42 DDI combinations that fall into this category were found. The most common DDIs were between anticoagulants and non-opioid analgesics, predominantly nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (diclofenac and ibuprofen); then between anticoagulants and antiplatelet drugs (acetylsalicylic acid and clopidogrel); and lastly, between anticoagulants and drugs for the treatment of mental disorders (sertraline, paroxetine, clozapine, and citalopram).

Interactions from risk category X were observed in 72 (36%) patients. Three DDIs from this risk category were detected in four patients. These were patients on extensive polypharmacy who received 10, 18, or 21 drugs. Only one of them had a severe clinical picture, while two had a mild and one a moderate clinical picture. The share of DDIs from risk category X in the total number of interactions (4.74%) was higher than in a study by Kilit et al. (2022), in which, among 605 DDIs in hospitalised COVID-19 patients, only three (0.5%) DDIs from risk

category X were detected. Analysing DDIs from risk category X, 13 DDI combinations that fall into this category were found. The combinations bilastine–azithromycin, diazepam–metronidazole, carbocisteine–metronidazole, promazine–lisinopril and hydrochlorothiazide, and furosemide–promazine had the highest frequency.

Conti et al. (2024) reported that the most frequent interactions involved nirmatrelvir/ritonavir and fluvoxamine, with over 80% of DDI-related adverse events identifiable using tools such as UpToDate® Lexidrug™ and Drugs.com. Conti et al. (2022) identified 575 DDIs among 58 drug combinations, with 26% of them detectable by all tools, 50% by at least one tool, and 24% remaining undetected, highlighting the need for multiple interaction checkers. Manjhi et al. (2021) found that all patients had at least one clinically significant DDI, most commonly related to hydroxychloroquine and azithromycin, and that additional drugs for comorbidities further increased that risk. Collectively, these studies emphasised the importance of timely medication review and the involvement of clinical pharmacists in decision-making to prevent DDI-related adverse events.

Correlation analyses between the total number of DDIs and, respectively, the total number of drugs, the total number of comorbidities/diagnoses, and the age of the patients were performed. Fig. 1 shows the correlation between the total number of DDIs and the total number of drugs for each patient. There was a very strong positive correlation. Fig. 2 shows the correlation between the total number of DDIs and the total number of comorbidities/diagnoses for each patient. There was a strong positive correlation. Fig. 3 shows the correlation between the total number of DDIs and the age of each patient. There was a weak positive correlation.

Figure 1. The scatterplot of the correlation between the total number of drug–drug interactions (DDIs) and the total number of drugs for each patient.

Figure 2. The scatterplot of the correlation between the total number of drug–drug interactions (DDIs) and the total number of comorbidities/diagnoses for each patient.

Figure 3. The scatterplot of the correlation between the total number of drug–drug interactions (DDIs) and the age of each patient.

A very strong positive correlation between the number of DDIs and the number of drugs is expected, considering that in numerous clinical studies a higher frequency of DDIs has been determined in patients receiving multiple drugs (Brandariz-Nuñez et al. 2020; Iloanusi et al. 2021; Kilit et al. 2022; Spanakis et al. 2022). In this context, it is necessary to rationalise drug use, in which a clinical pharmacist has a vital role, especially in the geriatric population. A strong positive correlation between the number of DDIs and the number of comorbidities that the patients had in addition to COVID-19 infection is also expected, given that a greater number of comorbidities requires treatment with more drugs. Like polypharmacy, comorbidities represent a risk factor independently associated with the development of DDIs. Almost three-quarters of patients (72.5%) in our study had a comorbidity, and their number varied from one to 11. The association between the number of DDIs and the number of comorbidities in COVID-19 patients was also established in other studies (Awortwe and Cascorbi 2020; Rahmadani et al. 2023). The positive but weak correlation between the number of DDIs and the age of the patients found in our study could be explained by the fact that the majority of patients, regardless of the severity of the clinical picture, were over 60 years old; that is, the patients were relatively homogeneous in terms of age structure.

The Kruskal–Wallis test was used to verify the existence of a statistically significant difference in the total number of DDIs and the total number of drugs, taking into account the severity of the clinical picture at admission. The results are shown in Table 2. There was a statistically significant difference in the total number of DDIs and the total number of drugs in patients with different severities of the clinical picture; that is, patients with a severe clinical picture had the highest total number of DDIs and the highest total number of drugs. Then, a *post hoc* analysis using the Bonferroni test was performed for the variables for which the previous test showed a statistically significant difference. The results are presented in Table 3. The total number of DDIs was statistically significantly higher in patients with a severe compared to patients with a mild clinical picture, as well as in patients with a severe compared to patients with a moderate clinical picture. The total number of drugs was statistically significantly higher in patients with a severe compared to patients with a mild clinical picture.

Table 2. Kruskal–Wallis test of the total number of drug–drug interactions (DDIs) and the total number of drugs, taking into account the severity of the clinical picture at admission.

Variable	Clinical picture	\bar{x} rank	H	p
Total number of drug–drug interactions (DDIs)	Mild	89.07	10.883	0.004
	Moderate	96.33		
	Severe	122.00		
Total number of drugs	Mild	89.61	12.854	0.002
	Moderate	93.96		
	Severe	124.31		

Table 3. *Post hoc* Bonferroni test of differences in the total number of drug–drug interactions (DDIs) and the total number of drugs, taking into account the severity of the clinical picture at admission.

Variable	Clinical pictures	Bonferroni	p
Total number of drug–drug interactions (DDIs)	Mild–Moderate	0.615	1.000
	Mild–Severe	9.890	0.005
	Moderate–Severe	6.804	0.027
Total number of drugs	Mild–Moderate	0.283	0.849
	Mild–Severe	0.002	0.007
	Moderate–Severe	0.049	0.148

This is a “vicious circle” because patients with a severe clinical picture have a greater number of comorbidities, which then requires the use of more drugs, and a larger number of drugs administered simultaneously presents a risk factor for DDIs.

If the number of DDIs from risk category B (no action required) ($n = 445$) is subtracted from the total number of DDIs recorded in 200 COVID-19 patients in our study ($n = 1689$), the result suggests that up to 1244 DDIs could potentially be prevented through timely intervention by a healthcare professional, such as a clinical pharmacist, and indicates that involving a clinical pharmacist as a core member of the healthcare team in clinical decision-making may be beneficial. A clinical pharmacist should play a central role in managing adverse effects, interactions, contraindications, and other aspects of rational and safe drug use. Unfortunately, the results of a study by Jia et al. (2021) showed that the integration of clinical pharmacists into healthcare teams is weak, with inadequate communication with other healthcare professionals, although they had a positive role in providing information and consultation about drugs, especially in the case of more vulnerable patients, and identifying adverse effects. On the other hand, in a study by Al-Quteimat et al. (2022), physicians accepted pharmacists’ interventions at a rate of 94.7%. Such a high acceptance rate indicates physicians’ trust in the quality of pharmaceutical care and highlights the recognised value of clinical pharmacists’ contributions. Physicians showed a high acceptance rate of services provided by pharmacists, ranging from 88.5% to 95.5%, in a study by Ahmed et al. (2022). This study highlighted the positive impact of clinical pharmacists in the care of COVID-19 patients, with physicians placing

considerable trust in their recommendations. In addition, pharmacist-driven antimicrobial interventions showed a relatively high acceptance rate from physicians (Nasr et al. 2023). In a study by Spanakis et al. (2022), a reduction in the number of clinically significant DDIs was observed during hospitalisation compared to hospital admission. The above can be attributed to the fact that specialised multidisciplinary healthcare teams had additional clinical information, such as laboratory findings and complete drug lists, which allowed them to be more aligned with evidence-based clinical guidelines in the provision of healthcare and proceed with better risk-benefit analysis and, consequently, fewer medication errors (Perez et al. 2022).

Conclusion

The risk of DDIs should be systematically assessed when starting the treatment of COVID-19 patients who are already receiving therapy, as well as those in whom polypharmacy is necessary due to the endangerment or failure of different organs caused by the progression of the disease. Regarding pharmacokinetic DDIs, thorough knowledge of drug characteristics associated with enzymes or transporters involved in drug metabolism (substrate, inhibitor, or inducer) allows prediction of the risk of increasing or decreasing drug exposure. The risk of pharmacodynamic DDIs originates from additive or antagonistic drug effects. Knowing the mechanisms of action of concomitantly administered drugs, as well as their safety profiles, can help predict risk so that treatment is adjusted or an appropriate therapeutic alternative is suggested. Given the high frequency of polypharmacy observed in our study and its link to adverse clinical outcomes in COVID-19 patients, future research should focus on thorough medication review and de-prescribing, particularly in elderly patients whose drug clearance is affected by age-related physiological changes. Investigating the early integration of clinical pharmacists' interventions in COVID-19 patients may help prevent disease progression and improve clinical outcomes.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: University of Sarajevo - Faculty of Pharmacy.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

N.O.Ć, T.B., N.Ž.S. and S.Š. gave substantial contributions to the conception or design of the work in the acquisition or interpretation of data. N.O.Ć and H.Ć. performed a statistical analysis of data. N.O.Ć and S.Š. had a part in preparing the article for drafting or critically revising it for its important intellectual content. All authors gave final approval of the version to be published.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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